

Assessment of Landscape and Coastal Ecosystem Risk Levels Due to Tourism Activities in the Ciletuh-Palabuhanratu National Geopark, West Java

Ankiq Taofiqurohman¹
M. Rudyansyah Ismail¹
Sheila Zallesa¹

¹ Department of Marine Science, Faculty of Fisheries and Marine Science.
Padjadjaran University

Corresponding author: ankiq@unpad.ac.id

Citation :

Taofiqurohman, A., Ismail, M. R., & Zallesa, S. (2024). Assessment of Landscape and Coastal Ecosystem Risk Levels Due to Tourism Activities in the Ciletuh-Palabuhanratu National Geopark, West Java. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10622437>

Abstract

The Ciletuh-Palabuhanratu UNESCO Global Geopark (CPUGG) is one of the National Strategic Tourism Areas in Indonesia. As a tourist destination, the coast in CPUGG is feared to experience ecosystem pressure due to the increase in visitor numbers and physical development to support tourism facilities and infrastructure. This study aims to assess the impact risk of tourism activities on the landscape and ecosystem in the coastal area of CPUGG. Information about the impact risk value is needed as a preliminary step to identify the tourism activities that most significantly affect the landscape and ecosystem. Moreover, by applying impact risk assessments on several tourist beaches in CPUGG, it is hoped to identify which beaches have landscapes and ecosystems in concerning conditions. Data from the impact risk analysis are needed as input in managing ecosystem-based management, which is part of the implementation of sustainable tourism development. Data in this research were collected through interview techniques as well as direct observations and measurements in the field. Initial observation results identified seven human activities that pose a risk of causing environmental pressure in CPUGG.

Introduction

Tourism potential areas can vitalize local economies by fostering small to medium enterprises, reducing unemployment, enhancing community incomes, and increasing Local Original Revenue (PAD) for further regional development and welfare. However, tourism development, aligned with population growth and rapid coastal area development for various uses, intensifies ecological pressures on landscapes and coastal ecosystems, threatening their existence and sustainability. Coastal landscapes and ecosystems, unique unions formed by the hydrosphere, lithosphere, and biosphere, face three main characteristics: convergence zones of land, sea, and air dynamics; buffer zones and habitats for diverse biological resources; and high fertility sources of organic matter.

The Ciletuh-Palabuhanratu National Geopark in Sukabumi, West Java, recognized as a UNESCO Global Geopark (Muslim et al., 2019), exemplifies sustainable management of geological, biodiversity, and cultural heritage for conservation, education, and economic purposes. It comprises three geo-areas with thematic focuses: Cisolok for Magmatic Track Shift, Jampang/Simpenan for Jampang Plateau Landscape, and Ciletuh for Subduction Fossils (Pusat Penelitian Geopark dan Kebencanaan Geologi Universitas Padjadjaran, 2017), thereby extending the geopark into the National Geopark Ciletuh-Palabuhanratu (GNCP). These areas, featuring about 117 km of coastal zone with various tourist beaches, attract significant visitor numbers, with 967,311 tourists recorded from January to November 2017 (Sule, 2020), underscoring the need for adequate infrastructure to support tourism while mitigating ecological pressure.

Unchecked exploitation can lead to environmental degradation, diminishing tourist attractions, and threatening coastal ecosystems. Environmental health risk factors also significantly contribute to global disease burdens, necessitating ecosystem-based management approaches for tourism areas (Ezzati et al., 2004; Limbong & Soetomo, 2014). Assessing coastal landscapes and ecosystems can address these challenges by evaluating their impact on coastal security, aesthetics, recreation, and tourism (Burke et al., 2017). A coastal landscape management approach integrates ecosystem integrity, coastal geomorphology, and human activities to mitigate biodiversity loss and physical damage. Risk assessment is crucial in applying these management strategies, emphasizing the need for indicator identification, reference condition measurement, and management alternative evaluation.

In Indonesia, the application of landscape and ecosystem-based management using Impact Risk Scores to identify environmental risks across human activities is rare, yet essential for assessing the overall environmental impact of tourism activities (Borgwardt et al., 2019). Research by Borgwardt et al. (2019) on the variability of Impact Risk Scores in European coastal areas reveals a positive correlation between landscape changes, ecosystem disruption, and the impact risk of human activities. Unsustainable tourism development risks environmental quality and has broader impacts on social, economic, and health aspects of communities.

Aims and Objectives

The purpose of this study is to:

- Identify tourism activities that pose risks and their impacts on the landscape and coastal ecosystems in CPUGG.
- Assess the risk level of various tourism activities and their pressure on the landscape and coastal ecosystems in CPUGG.
- Compare the risk level of each tourist beach in CPUGG.

Literature Review

Overview of CPUGG

Ciletuh is a bay located on the south-west coast of Sukabumi. The name Ciletuh is derived from the name of a large river that flows into the Ciletuh bay, surrounded by cliffs that form a horseshoe shape with the highest peak at 360 m, spanning 12 km in length and 7 km in width. Along this fault, there are 8 waterfalls. Viewed from above, Ciletuh appears like a giant natural amphitheater. The Ciletuh area falls within the Jampang region, which includes Ciletuh, Cilacap, Ujung Genteng, Surade, Cikaso, Jampang Tengah, and Jampang Kulon.

The Ciletuh-Palabuhanratu National Geopark spans 126,100 hectares or 1,261 km², covering 74 villages in 8 districts: Ciracap, Surade, Ciemas, Waluran, Simpenan, Palabuhanratu, Cikakak, and Cisolok, divided into three geo-areas: Ciletuh, Jampang, and Cisolok (Rosana, 2016). In Ciletuh, there are rock groups considered the oldest in Java Island. The existence of the geopark makes this area geologically unique and rare. The exposed rocks in Ciletuh offer an exotic view, both in terms of rock composition and nature. These are evidence of natural processes, especially geology, which are a pride of the West Java Province (Rosana, 2016). The geopark area is located in the Ciemas District, covering the villages of Taman Jaya, Mekar Sakti, Ciwaru, and Mandra Jaya with an area of 10,221 ha, rice fields of 2,570.00 ha, and dry land of 3,070.00 ha. The borders are: North with Simpenan District, South with the Indian Ocean, East with Ciracap District, and West with the Indian Ocean. Additionally, GNCP tourist attractions offer beach views with white sand and waterfalls surrounded by forests and feature traditional villages as a unique attraction. From its highlands, tourists can enjoy the beautiful Ciletuh valley with the Indian Ocean and small islands around its coast in the background. There is also a turtle conservation area at Ujung Genteng Beach.

Impact Risk

Uncontrolled tourism activities can pose threats to the environment. According to UNEP (United Nations Environment Programme), the main environmental impacts of tourism are divided into three major points: depletion of natural resources, increased pollution, and impacts on ecosystems. Tourism activities can create significant pressure on local resources, such as energy, water, forests, land, and wildlife. Other impacts include pollution, such as air emissions, noise, solid waste, liquid waste, and visual pollution. Emissions from transportation and energy production can lead to acid rain, photochemical pollution, and, on a global level, contribute to global warming. Noise pollution can also alter wildlife behavior towards their natural activity patterns, indirectly changing nature and its behavior.

The World Health Organization (2004) defines risk analysis as the process of estimating risks to a target organism, system, or subpopulation aimed at providing a scientific framework to assist decision-makers and stakeholders (legislators and regulators, industry, and concerned citizens) in addressing environmental and health issues. In an ecosystem-based management approach, interactions between human activities and pressures need to be identified first to understand the full range of activities producing pressure. Risk assessment plays a crucial role in operationalizing ecosystem-based management approaches. The next step is crucial to identify indicators, measure reference conditions, and evaluate management alternatives (Borgwardt et al., 2019).

One method is using the Impact Risk value, which is used to identify the environmental impact risks across all human activities (impact chains) by first weighing interactions according to five criteria: spatial extent, dispersal potential, frequency of interaction, persistence of pressure, and severity of interaction. In this risk assessment, risks from human activities across landscapes and ecosystems are explored in detail. In short, all activities and all pressures resulting from activities that interact with one or more ecosystem components in a landscape in the case study will be identified. A total Impact Risk (IR) score for each ecosystem component is required by summing scores across all activities and pressures (summing all impact chains per ecosystem component) (Borgwardt et al., 2019; Knights et al., 2015).

Methodology

The initial data sources consist of secondary data obtained from departments or agencies related to the research. Interviews with several informants were also used as an additional source of information. The interviews utilized the Purposive Sampling method with a snowball type to obtain recommendations from key informants involved in environmental and tourism activities. Additionally, in-depth interviews will be conducted with several informants considered to be very familiar with the issues, aimed at uncovering necessary facts not found during the research process. The interviews are planned to be conducted twice with at least 12 participants who are figures related to tourism activities, ranging from youth and community leaders, tourism entrepreneurs, environmental activists, to government employees dealing with tourism and environmental issues. This is in line with the theory by Schuhmann et al. (2019), which considers about 12 participants in a group to be sufficient because the level of saturation is generally achieved. Data collection is aimed at:

a. Determination of Coastal Ecological Components

In this study, the typology of ecological components is determined based on what is commonly applied in coastal and marine environments and is considered representative of a healthy ecosystem (Knights et al., 2015). Google Imagery is also used to view the boundaries of areas to create a map of ecological components.

b. Identification of Community Activities Related to Tourism

Initial data sources consist of secondary data obtained from departments or agencies related to the research. Spatial data and interviews with related informants are also used as additional information. The community activities identified are those related to tourism in the ecosystem area.

c. Identification of Pressures Causing Risks

After establishing which activities will be observed, identification is carried out to see the types of pressures that pose risks to each determined ecological component. Each identified impact is given an interaction criterion value based on spatial extent, dispersal potential, frequency of interaction, pressure persistence, and severity of interaction.

Results and Outcomes Achieved

Initial Survey

This initial survey was conducted only along the Ciletuh coastline, specifically on the outer part of the Palabuhanratu bay (Figure 1). From the initial survey in the coastal area of the CPUGG, 15 beaches were identified as Areas of Interest (AoI). The coordinates and names of the beaches in the AoI are shown in Table 1.

Figure 1. The area of interest

Table 1. Beaches coordinate

No	Name	Coordinate
1	Pantai Karang Bolong	7°24'45"S 106°34'56"E
2	Pantai Cikaret	7°25'02"S 106°34'06"E
3	Pantai Minajaya	7°24'00"S 106°31'00"E
4	Pantai Karang Trisna	7°23'52"S 106°30'47"E
5	Pantai Karang Gantungan	7°22'50"S 106°29'36"E
6	Pantai Tebing Pengantin	7°22'24"S 106°28'46"E
7	Pantai Pamunguan	7°22'20"S 106°28'37"E
8	Pantai Taman Pandan	7°22'12"S 106°27'52"E
9	Pantai Cinta Bersemi	7°22'08"S 106°27'41"E
10	Pantai Tenda Biru	7°22'56"S 106°24'24"E
11	Pantai Ujung Genteng	7°22'22"S 106°24'03"E
12	Pantai Cibuaya	7°20'49"S 106°24'09"E
13	Pantai Pangumbahan	7°20'11"S 106°23'54"E
14	Pantai Pasir Putih	7°19'55"S 106°23'51"E

Initial Observation Results

Based on field observations, there are 7 sectors causing environmental pressures in the AoI, classified using the Options for Delivering Ecosystem-Based Marine Management (ODEMM) approach. Each sector produces several activities that cause pressure. The relationship between the sectors, the number of activities, and the pressures generated is shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Sector and pressure linkages

	Aquaculture	Fishing	Shipping	Power station	Infra-structure	Agri-culture	Tourism
Smothering	2	1		1	2		2
Sealing	2			1	2		1
Changes in siltation	4	1		2	3	1	4
Abrasion	4	2	1	1	3		6
Selective Extraction of Non-living Resources				1			1
Underwater noise	4	8	2	1	3		9
Marine Litter	4	4	1	1			7
Thermal changes				1			
Introduction of Synthetic compounds	4	3	1	2	1	1	5
Introduction of Non-synthetic compounds	3	3	1	1		1	4
Nitrogen and Phosphorus enrichment	1					1	1
Input of organic matter	2	4				1	4
Introduction of microbial pathogens	2	2	1		1	1	1
Introduction of NIS and translocations	2	2	1		1		1

Selective extraction of species	2	8					2
Death or injury by collision		2	1				3
Barrier to species movement		2					
Water flow rate changes				1	1		1
pH changes	1					1	

References

- Borgwardt, F., L. Robinson, D. Trauner, H. Teixeira, A. J.A. Nogueira, A. I. Lillebø, G. Piet, M. Kuemmerlen, T. O'Higgins, H. McDonald, J. Arevalo Torres, A. L. Barbosa, A. Iglesias Campos, T. Hein, F. Culhane. 2019. Exploring variability in environmental impact risk from human activities across aquatic ecosystems. *Science of the Total Environment* 652: 12 hlm.
- Burke, L. M., Reytar, K., Spalding, M., & Perry, A. 2017. *Reefs at Risk Revisited: World Resources Institute*
- Ezzati, M., A. D. Lopez, A. Rodgers, and C. J. L. Murray, eds. 2004. *Comparative Quantification of Health Risks: Global and Regional Burden of Diseases Attributable to Selected Major Risk Factors*. Geneva: WHO.
- Knights, A.M., Piet, G.J., Jongbloed, R.H., Tamis, J.E., White, L., Akoglu, E., Boicenco, L., Churilova, T., Kryvenko, O., Fleming-Lehtinen, V., Leppanen, J.M., Galil, B.S., Goodsir, F., Goren, M., Margonski, P., Moncheva, S., Oguz, T., Papadopoulou, K.N., Setälä, O., Smith, C.J., Stefanova, K., Timofte, F., Robinson, L.A., 2015. An exposure- effect approach for evaluating ecosystem wide risks from human activities. *ICES J. Mar. Sci.* 72, 1105–1115.
- Limbong, F., & S. Soetomo. 2014. Dampak Perkembangan Pariwisata Terhadap Lingkungan Taman Nasional Karimunjawa. *Jurnal Ruang*, 2(1): 10 hlm.
- Muslim, D., E. Haerani, F. N. Muslim, G. O. Muslim. 2019. Toward the safe live-able built environment around Ciletuh-Palabuhanratu Geopark Area in Sukabumi Regency, Indonesia. *IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environment Science* 248(1), 012036.
- Pusat Penelitian Geopark dan Kebencanaan Geologi Universitas Padjadjaran. 2017. *Geopark Ciletuh-Palabuhanratu Menuju Unesco Global Geopark, Bagaimana Unpad Berkontribusi?*. Universitas Padjadjaran. Bandung
- Rosana, Mega F. 2008. Geologi Kawasan Ciletuh Sukabumi, *Bulletin Scientific Contrubution*, Vol.6 (2), 111-119
- Schuhmann, P., Skeete, R., Waite, R., Bangwayo-Skeete, P., Casey, J., Oxenford, H. A., & Gill, D. A. 2019. Coastal and Marine Quality and Tourists Stated Intention to Return to Barbados. *Water*, 11(6), 1265
- Sule, E.T. 2020. Effect Of Tourist Characteristics And Resources On Image: Study Of Ciletuh Geodiversity Area Sukabumi. *Jurnal Bisnis dan Manajemen*, Vol. 21 (2)